

Lemon (*Citrus limon*) Peel Stain Remover as a Sustainable Alternative to Commercial Stain Remover

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ABSTRACT

Lemon peels are known to have antimicrobial and antifungal properties. The aim of this study is to compare the effectiveness of using lemon peels as a sustainable alternative against commercially made stain remover, thereby addressing the ecological concerns and environmental impact associated with the widespread use of commercial products. The test was conducted on three different types of stains: Milo, coffee, and soy sauce, each on a 10 cm × 10 cm cloth for both commercial-based (Domex) and peel-based stain cleaners. The results of the experiment conducted on the liquid chocolate-stained cloth showed a mean gray value with the lemon peel cleaner at approximately 0.12% greater than its commercial counterpart. In comparison, the latter is 3.3% and 4% ahead in soy sauce and coffee stains, respectively. Moreover, the analysis of the descriptive statistics of the outputs showed several key differences between the lemon peel-based cleaner and the commercial cleaner, i.e. the commercial cleaner is more consistent at removing stains overall than the lemon peel-based cleaner. Statistical analyses revealed that while lemon peel can be used as an adequate homemade sustainable alternative to commercial cleaners, it is not more effective.

INTRODUCTION

Worldwide citrus fruit production reached an estimated 75.54 million tons in 2018 (Michael-Igolima et al., 2023). Approximately 20% (15.10 million tons) is turned into fruit waste, including peels, pulp, and seeds. In the Philippines alone, citrus production reached an estimated 30,000 tons on average from 2012–2014, 1,800 tons (6%) of which were fruit peels (Soriano et al., 2021). As per Maksoud et al. (2021), they can cause serious problems with the disposal and can greatly pollute the environment since only a small amount is utilized and the

remaining bulk is burned. Generally, nearly 50-60% of citrus fruits are wasted during industrial processing, including peels, seeds, and membrane residue (Khan et al., 2021).

Chemical cleaning products significantly increase water pollution (Barua et al., 2022; Azizullah et al., 2021). Pollutants, such as surfactants and detergents, disrupt biological processes, pose toxicity risks to various species, and generally present a detrimental effect on aquatic organisms (Zhang et al., 2022). Additionally, Gheorghe et al. (2019) stated that the excretion and leakage of cleaning agents into water systems may result in eutrophication and impact the surrounding water quality.

“Green Cleaning” is a term used to characterize cleaning to safeguard health without endangering the environment (Cosgrove, 2018). According to a survey conducted by Filho et al. (2022), ever since the second wave of the pandemic, individuals have been more aware and adamant about purchasing sustainable or “green” products. Based on the same study, 58.3% of individuals who responded to the survey considered the sustainable production of a product very important, with the other 41.7% considering it important. To keep up with the increase in demand for “green” products, studies about the possibility of creating more sustainable stain cleaners have emerged. In studies by Amorado et al. (2021) and Michael-Igolima et al. (2023), orange peels were used to create a sustainable cleaning product with accessible ingredients. A study done by Jangra et. al (2023) concluded that while homemade textile stain removers may not yet be as versatile as commercial treatments, they are still viable enough in order to engage in a more environmentally friendly lifestyle.

Lemon peels have garnered significant attention due to their robust antimicrobial properties against microorganisms, including Gram-positive bacteria like *S. aureus*, Gram-negative bacteria like *E. coli*, and fungi such as *C. albicans* and *T. rubrum* (Irfan et al.,

2019). This antimicrobial efficacy, coupled with the astringent nature of lemon peel extracts, positions them as significant contributors to the development of effective cleaning formulations. Studies have demonstrated the antibacterial activity of methanolic extracts derived from various citrus fruit peels, showcasing their efficacy against pathogens (Hasan et al., 2022). The high acidity of lemon peels, attributed to the presence of citric acid, shows their efficacy as natural cleaners (Fernandes et al., 2022). Additionally, citric acid, a valuable constituent of citrus peels, serves as a potent antimicrobial agent (Hasan et al., 2022).

Citric acid, the most abundant organic acid in lemons, has properties and advantages that contribute to the fruit's potential as a sustainable stain cleaner. Citrus fruits are classified as acid fruits because they contain a sufficient amount of citric acid (Jamil et al., 2015). According to the same study, Citrus fruits' acid contents may vary over the ripeness of the fruit, the citric acid content of different citrus fruits ranges from 2.6-8%. Citric acid's naturally low pH level creates an unfavorable environment for bacterial growth and disrupts the contaminants' nucleic acid bonds and precipitates proteins (Winarto et al., 2021). Additionally, fruits of the Citrus genus are sample sources of flavonoids, specifically naringenin, which possess antibacterial properties (Medina-Rodriguez et al., 2020).

This research aimed to compare the effectiveness of using lemon peels as a sustainable alternative against commercially made stain remover, thereby addressing the ecological concerns and environmental impact associated with the widespread use of commercial products.

The following research hypotheses were tested in this study:

H₀: There is no significant difference between the mean gray values of the stained pieces of cloth before and after treatment using lemon peel-based stain cleaner.

H₀: There is no significant difference between the mean gray values of the stained pieces of cloth treated using lemon peel-based stain cleaner and commercial stain cleaner.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methodologies of the study were adapted from the studies of Amorado et al. (2021) and Jangra et al. (2023).

Stain preparation

1 yard of cotton cloth was bought from Biñan, Laguna, Public Market. This cloth was then cut into six pieces of 10 cm × 10 cm, three pieces of cloth for both the lemon peel-based stain cleaner and commercial-based (Domex) stain cleaner. Two pieces of cloth were allocated for the Milo stain, two pieces of cloth were allocated for the coffee stain, and two pieces of cloth were allocated for the soy sauce stain. Each piece of cloth was swatched with the corresponding stains and was air-dried for 1 hour to ensure proper staining. The stained cloths were then scanned using a Brother DCP-T720W Printer.

Collection and processing of lemon

348 grams worth of lemons were bought from Biñan, Laguna, Public Market to ensure uniform source condition. The 348 grams of collected lemons were then peeled and the extracted juices were repurposed to not be wasted.

Production of lemon peel-based stain remover

Maceration was carried out with the help of a food processor to ensure the fineness of the cumulated peels. Since lemon peels contain citric acid, which exhibits antibacterial and antioxidant effects (Rienoviar et al., 2022), maceration is done to ensure maximum extraction of citric acid from the lemon peels. After the processing, the fine lemon peels presented 114 grams of stain remover. The testing of the stain remover on three different types of stains, namely:

Milo, coffee, and soy sauce each on a 10 cm × 10 cm cloth for both commercial-based (Domex) and lemon peel-based stain remover was conducted.

Treatment of stains

Each treatment was assigned one piece of cloth from each type of stain. One tablespoon of the treatment was applied to their respective pieces of stained cloth. The respective treatments were hand rubbed into the cloth for 15 seconds, then left alone for 1 minute. After the elapsed time, the pieces of cloth were washed for 30 seconds and then air dried.

Finding the mean gray values of the stains

The cloths underwent a post-scanning process utilizing ImageJ software for image processing. Utilizing the scanned analysis of the stained cloths prior to the experiment and image results after the experiment, ImageJ was then employed to split the color channels of the scanned images, thereby facilitating a thorough examination of the effects of both the commercial-based stain cleaner (Domex) and lemon-peel based stain cleaner on the chosen stains. This approach aimed to minimize margins of error by discerning disparities in mean gray values across each grayscale color channel, namely: red, green, and blue. The mean gray value (MGV) of each color channel was then analyzed. In this context, a higher MGV corresponded to a reduced presence of stains, while a lower MGV indicated a greater extent of staining.

A dependent samples *t*-test was applied to compare the MGVs of the cloth before and after the use of lemon-peel stain cleaner, and an independent *t*-test was applied to compare the MGVs of the cloth after application of the lemon-peel stain cleaner and commercial stain cleaner (Domex).

RESULTS

The cloths were scanned before and after receiving treatment in order to assess the effectiveness of the lemon peels as a stain remover as compared to the commercially available one. The tables below show the performance of lemon peels as compared to the commercial cleaner with regard to their ability to remove stains. Both batches were analyzed using ImageJ, where the MGV was calculated per RGB color channel in order to minimize the margin of error and provide more accurate results. A higher MGV indicates a brighter stain, meaning less of the stain is visible. The findings were then recorded (Table 1.1 and Table 1.2).

Table 1.1. Observations before treatment

Batch	Stain	Color Channel	Mean Gray Value
1	Coffee	Red	216.3559941
		Green	204.4160613
		Blue	201.6037331
	Liquid Chocolate	Red	224.6994017
		Green	212.3097837
		Blue	211.7649736
	Soy Sauce	Red	217.209659
		Green	193.7498049
		Blue	174.1888593
2	Coffee	Red	215.2749563
		Green	204.1214069
		Blue	201.460433
	Liquid Chocolate	Red	225.1725167
		Green	212.9699676
		Blue	212.8322365
	Soy Sauce	Red	217.327081
		Green	192.6419994
		Blue	173.1035829

Table 1.2. Observations after treatment

Cleaner	Stain	Color Channel	Mean Gray Value
Lemon Peel	Coffee	Red	227.7967997
		Green	223.1614959
		Blue	224.0453199
	Liquid Chocolate	Red	235.5372835
		Green	232.141675
		Blue	234.4131274
	Soy Sauce	Red	232.2899412
		Green	229.4965812
		Blue	230.1518729
Commercial Cleaner	Coffee	Red	234.0362855
		Green	232.698345
		Blue	236.3313421
	Liquid Chocolate	Red	234.3285584
		Green	232.272167
		Blue	234.6266002
	Soy Sauce	Red	237.3587305
		Green	237.3673996
		Blue	240.9232482

Following either the lemon peel cleaner or the commercial cleaner treatment, there was a noticeable increase in brightness for all samples. In comparison to the cleaner made from lemon peels, the computed MGV of the coffee-stained cloth with the commercial cleaner was higher by approximately 4%. The soy sauce-stained cloth showed similar findings but with a 3.3% difference instead. Unlike the previous two samples, however, the results of the experiment conducted on the liquid chocolate-stained fabric showed an MGV with the lemon peel cleaner at approximately 0.12% greater than its commercial counterpart.

Figure 1. Descriptives of analyzed cloth after lemon peel treatment and commercial treatment

The analysis of the descriptive statistics of the outputs revealed several key differences between the lemon peel-based cleaner and the commercial cleaner. Specifically, the mean MGCV of the lemon peel-based cleaner was 2.4% smaller compared to the commercial cleaner, and its median MGCV was 1.9% less. Moreover, the standard deviation of the lemon peel-based cleaner was 57% larger. Additionally, the minimum and maximum MGCVs of the lemon peel-based cleaner were 3.9% and 2.2% smaller, respectively, than those of the commercial cleaner.

DISCUSSION

The study aimed to find out if lemon peels were viable as a sustainable homemade alternative stain remover wherein there would be a significant difference between the MGCVs of the stains before and after treatment, and if it would have a significant difference from the performance of the commercial stain cleaner (Domex).

Based on the data shown in *Table 1.2*, the findings demonstrated that while the lemon peel cleaner worked better on the liquid chocolate (Milo) stains, the commercial cleaner is more effective against stains from coffee and soy sauce. The potential of the lemon peel cleaner as a feasible alternative for its commercial counterpart is demonstrated by the relatively small difference between the results of the two cleaners.

Referencing *Figure 1*, the commercial treatment generally has a higher mean and median MGV and lower standard deviation, implying that it is more consistent than the lemon peel-based stain cleaner.

The result of the dependent samples *t*-test implies that the lemon peel stain remover is effective in dealing with the Milo, coffee, and soy sauce stains. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected, and there is a significant difference between the MGVs of the pieces of cloth before and after treatment.

The result of the independent samples *t*-test showed that the commercial stain cleaner is better than the homemade lemon peel-based stain cleaner; therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. There is a significant difference between the MGVs of the stained pieces of cloth treated using lemon peel-based stain cleaner and commercial stain cleaner. Consistent with the study of Jangra et. al (2023), this implies that while lemon peel-based stain cleaner can be used as a sufficient homemade sustainable alternative to commercial stain cleaners, it is not more effective. However, they are still effective for those who wish to use a more sustainable homemade alternative to commercial stain cleaners.

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APPENDIX

Appendix A: Stain Preparation

Appendix B: Processing of Lemons

Appendix C: Production of Lemon Peel-Based Stain Remover

Appendix D: Lemon Peel-Based Stain Remover

Appendix E: Application of Stain Removers

Appendix F: Pieces of Cloth Post-Treatment

